

Integrated germplasm improvement—rainfed lowland

Performance of new rice cultivars in monsoon season in central Kerala, India

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Performance and adaptability of new rice cultivars Makam, Remya, Kanakam (Moncompu), and Jayathy (Pattambi)

were studied in central Kerala under several on-farm lowland situations varying from irrigated transplanted to rainfed dry sown. Soils ranged from sandy to clayey loam. Trials were conducted in 1991 and 1992 kharif (monsoon) seasons. Eight replications were laid out in fields of eight farmers at each location (Table 1).

The cultivars outyielded the checks at all locations, showing their adaptability to a range of conditions. Agronomic traits and general characteristics of the cultivars are in Table 2.

Table 1. Grain yield at several locations in central Kerala, India, 1991 and 1992 kharif.

Variety	Yield (t/ha)					Mean
	Kannambra	1991			Mean	
		Avinissery	Karukkully	Kalady		
Makam	6.4	5.7	3.9	3.5	4.9	
Remya	6.1	5.5	4.0	3.6	4.8	
Kanakam	5.6	5.7	3.6	3.4	4.6	
Jayathy	6.3	(white rice not preferred)				
Matta Triveni (check)	4.7	4.9	—	—	—	
Jyothy (check)	—	—	3.1	2.6	—	
Pavizham (check)	—	—	3.3	3.1	—	
LSD (0.05)	0.4	0.5	0.3	0.6		
1992						
	Alathur	Kozhalmannam	Wadakkanchery	Aluva	Mean	
Makam	5.3	4.9	3.9	4.8	4.7	
Remya	4.2	4.1	4.3	4.6	4.3	
Kanakam	5.2	4.9	4.6	4.1	4.7	
Jayathy	5.2	5.0	3.7	4.1	4.5	
Jyothy (check)	4.7	3.3	3.4	4.0	3.9	
LSD (0.05)	0.5	0.5	0.6	0.3		

Table 2. Agronomic traits of new rice cultivars under on-farm conditions, central Kerala, India, 1991 and 1992 kharif.

Variety	Pedigree	Kernel characters	Maturity (d)	Plant height (cm)	Panicles (no./hill)	Panicle length (cm)	1,000-grain wt (g)
Makam	MO 9 (ARC6650/Jaya)	Red short bold	120	83	6.2	21.0	23
Remya	MO10 (Jaya/PTB33)	Red short bold	119	88	5.7	24.7	30
Kanakam	MO 11 (IR1561/PTB33)	Red medium bold	121	87	5.0	26.0	30
Jayathy (1727)	PTB46 (Triveni/IR2061)	White	119	95	6.4	25.0	25

Integrated pest management—disease

Sheath rot (ShR) disease of rice in Punjab, Pakistan

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Dark brown lesions of diverse size and shape on flag leaf sheaths and partially emerged panicles in Basmati 385 were observed during 1990. Isolations from infected plant parts revealed the presence of *Sarocladium oryzae*.

To fulfill the requirements of Koch's postulates for pathogenicity, flag leaf sheaths were injected with 10-d-old culture 8-10 d before panicle emergence during 1991. Symptoms similar to those occurring under natural infection conditions were observed. Incidence was 79% in inoculated control and 15% in uninoculated control. Reisolation of infected tillers from both treatments confirmed *S. oryzae* to be the causal organism.

ShR incidence has increased with the cultivation of early-maturing, high-yielding, and susceptible Basmati 385. The highest disease incidence under natural infection conditions was 56.6% on Basmati 385, 27.1% on Basmati 370, 17.5% on Basmati 6129, and 25% on 4048 line. This is the first report of the disease in Punjab, Pakistan. ■